

Origin	Entries (no.)	Genotypes (no.) with given disease rating ^a		
		R (1-5%)	I (6-25%)	S (>25 %)
CIAT, Colombia	198	126	38	34
EMBRAPA, Brazil	16	15	1	0
Indonesia	91	0	10	81
IRRI, Philippines	132	35	64	33
Total	437	176	113	148

Local checks:
C22 (S): 100% dead
Danau Laut Tawar (R): 3, 4 (25%)

^a Disease severities evaluated according to disease damage index keys to estimate damage caused by major diseases of upland rice. R = resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible.

Pest resistance — insects

Evaluation of rice cultivars for resistance to leafhopper (LF)

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We screened 81 rice cultivars from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, for LF resistance 1986-87.

Entries were direct seeded in 4 × 1.05-m plots with two replications. Recommended agronomic practices were followed.

LF infestation was heavy 70 d after sowing, when the crop was in the booting to flowering stage. Susceptible check Brown gora had 90% infestation. Damaged and undamaged leaves of each test entry were counted in 1 m² of each replication, and averages calculated. Percentage damaged leaves was converted into 0-9 point scale:

$$\text{Scale} = \frac{\% \text{ damaged leaves in test cultivar}}{\% \text{ damaged leaves in susceptible check}}$$

In 1986, RP1714-111-7-3-2 and OR811-2 had no LF damage. In 1987, RD2599-150-18-8-5 and RAU156-56 had no damage.

Reactions of most cultivars changed in 1987. RP1714-111-7-3-2 and OR811-2, which had 0 damage in 1986, were evaluated at 3 in 1987.

Cultivars that scored 0, 1, and 3 both years could be treated as resistant and used in a crossing program (see table). ■

Cultivars that scored 0-3 for LF resistance. Ranchi, India, 1986 and 1987.

Score	Cultivars
	<i>1986</i>
0	RP1714-111-7-3-2, OR811-2
1	RP2217-71-73-14, RP2525-19-124, RP1888-132-24-11-8, RP2522-16-14-80, NDR119, UPR83-28, UPR83-20, NDK224, NDR222, BG367-4, and CN747-1-4
3	RP2415-203-5-1-2, RP2263-934-592-5, RP2235-35-40-50, RTN500, RP2423-5-77-16, TNAU301790, Akashi, TNAU81804, NRL502, TNAU83134, TNAU83108, NDR312-1, NR571-1, MAUSEL 10, RP2601-24-36-138, Pusa 510, JR35, OR811-10, RP2599-150-18-8-5, ADT85001, RAU151-56
	<i>1987</i>
0	RP2599-150-188-8-5, RAU151-56
1	OR811-10, ADT85001, RP2522-16-14-80, NDR119, UPR83-28, TNAU83108
3	RP1714-111-7-3-2, OR811-2, RP2217-71-73-14, RP2525-19-124, RP1888-132-24-11-8, UPR83-20, NDR224, NDR222, BG367-4, CN747-1-4, RP2415-203-5-1-2, RP2263-934-592-5, RTN500, RP2423-5-77-16, Akashi, Pusa 510, RAU4071-51-13, RAU4045-2A.

Stress tolerance — excess water

Inheritance of submergence tolerance in rice

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We traced inheritance of submergence tolerance in six submergence-tolerant advanced lines crossed with susceptible IR11288-B-B-69-1. Seeds of the parents, F₁, and F₂ were sown in 5 × 5-cm plastic pots and placed in galvanized iron trays in the glasshouse. Seedlings were pulled 35 d after sowing and tillers separated to test submergence tolerance. At 10 d after separation, trays containing potted tillers were put in a tank inside the greenhouse and the plants submerged to 90 cm for 12 d. Recovery was measured 7 d after submergence.

Submergence tolerance of the F₁ and F₂ was calculated by dividing their survival by the survival percentage of the tolerant parent.

Survival in the F₁ of four crosses tended toward the tolerant parent; survival in two crosses was very poor (see table). This implies that dominance of submergence tolerance varies.

Although survival of the F₁ of BKNFR76106-16-0-1/IR11288 was very poor, the F₂ showed tolerance (which was expected). The reason for the discrepancy in the F₁ is not clear.

Survival was higher in crosses involving strongly submergence-tolerant parents that derive their tolerance from FR13A or Kurkaruppan (BKNFR76106-13-2 and IR29012-4-1-3 from FR13A and IR31406-333-1 from Kurkaruppan). Survival was lower in the crosses involving moderately tolerant parents IR21567-16-2-2 and IR8234-OT-9-2 (they presumably obtained their genes for tolerance from moderately tolerant KLG6986 and Nam Sagui 19).

Reaction to submergence of parents and F₁ and F₂ populations of crosses.

Cross	Submergence survival (%)			v ²	Ratio	Probability
	Parents	F ₁	F ₂			
BKNFR76106-13-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	84.3 0.0	72	54	0.21	9:7	0.50-0.70
BKNFR76106-16-0-1/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	80.5 0.0	19	51	1.12	9:7	0.25-0.30
IR8234-0T-9-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	73.4 0.0	65	41	9.45	7:9	0.01-0.001
IR21567-16-2-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	76.0 0.0	32	35	3.50	7:9	0.05-0.10
IR29012-4-1-3/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	81.3 0.0	72	43	0.02	7:9	0.70-0.90
IR31406-333-1 IR11288-B-B-69-1	10.0 0.0	72	59	0.31	9:7	0.50-0.70

Two types of segregation ratios were observed in the F₂: 9:7 for crosses where tolerant parents derived tolerant genes from FR13A and Kurkaruppan, and 7:9 for crosses where tolerant parents derived

tolerant genes from moderately tolerant KLG986 and Nam Sagui 19. These ratios can be explained by the complementary action of at least two genes. ■

Stress tolerance – adverse soils

Genetic variability in rice genotypes planted in sodic soil

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We evaluated the genetic variability and heritability of desirable traits in 56 rice

genotypes sown Jul 1989 in sodic soil (pH 8.9).

Planting was done in 5-m rows with three 35-d-old seedlings/hill at 25- × 25-cm spacing. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Maximum and minimum temperatures during crop duration were 32.7-27.4 and 26.4-14.9 °C.

All traits except flag leaf thickness showed a wide range of phenotypic

Range, mean, coefficients of variability, heritability, and genetic advance of 16 traits in 56 rice genotypes grown in sodic soils. Faizabad, India, 1989.

Trait	Range	Grand mean and SE	PCV	GCV	ECV	Heritability (%)	Genetic advance in % of mean	
Plant height (cm)	67.9-145.0	90.4 p	3.2	15.9	15.3	4.3	92.7	30.4
Tillers per plant	3.4- 8.7	6.0 p	0.6	21.3	17.4	12.3	67.1	29.4
Flag leaf thickness (mm)	0.6- 1.3	0.9 p	0.02	16.7	16.3	2.0	95.7	33.0
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	18.3- 56.5	34.0 p	1.5	23.1	22.5	5.5	94.4	45.0
Days to panicle emergence	77.7-122.3	101.0 p	1.6	8.8	8.6	2.0	94.9	17.2
Days to 50% flowering	82.0-131.0	104.8 p	1.2	8.3	8.2	1.4	97.2	16.6
Days to maturity	103.0-155.0	136.8 p	1.8	9.8	9.7	1.6	97.5	19.8
Panicles per plant	2.8- 6.8	4.9 p	0.6	24.1	19.3	14.3	64.3	31.8
Panicle length (cm)	18.4- 28.1	23.5 p	0.9	9.0	7.8	4.6	74.1	13.8
Spikelets per panicle	61.7-270.7	137.2 p	13.9	33.0	30.5	14.4	85.9	58.4
Filled grains per panicle	52.0-239.3	117.4 p	14.4	32.9	29.3	15.1	79.1	53.6
Grain sterility (%)	5.0- 41.0	14.0 p	2.7	55.4	50.3	23.2	82.5	94.7
Biological yield per plant (g)	12.7- 45.3	25.8 p	3.4	33.4	29.2	16.2	76.4	52.3
Grain yield per plant (g)	6.8- 21.6	11.4 p	1.6	27.6	24.0	13.6	41.3	26.6
Harvest index (%)	29.7- 62.0	45.9 p	4.8	20.9	16.4	12.9	61.8	43.0
100-grain wt (g)	1.6- 3.3	2.6 p	0.1	13.9	13.5	3.1	92.3	23.3

variation (see table). The phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) was higher than the genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) for all traits. PCV ranged from 8.3 for days to 50% flowering to 55.4 for grain sterility.

Tillers/plant, flag leaf area, paniced plant, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, grain sterility, biological yield/plant, grain yield/plant, and harvest index had high values for both GCV and PCV.

Tillers/plant, panicles/plant, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, grain sterility, biological yield/plant, grain yield/plant, and harvest index showed higher environmental coefficient of variability (ECV). This indicates that these traits were more susceptible to environmental and agro-ecotypic factors, especially to soil sodicity and temperature variations.

Grain sterility showed higher PCV, GCV, ECV, and genetic advance (in % of mean) than other traits, indicating this trait could be used in breeding for salt tolerance. Heritability was high for all traits except grain yield/plant.

Grain sterility, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, biological yield/plant, flag leaf area, and harvest index showed higher values for genetic advance.

Panicles/plant, flag leaf area, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, sterility, and yield may be good selection criteria for screening rice genotypes for sodic soil conditions. ■

Absorption of nutrients and their replaceable functions in rice varieties tolerant of and sensitive to K deficiency

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The experiment was conducted with two varieties: Xiang-Zao-Nuo 1 (XZN 1) is tolerant of K deficiency, Shuang-Gui 36 (SG36) is sensitive. Seedlings at the three-leaf stage were grown on complete and K-deficient nutrient solutions. Dry weight of seedlings was determined 34, 38, and 41 d after planting. Content of Cu, Mn, Zn, Fe, Mg, K, Na, and Ca in dried shoots was analyzed.

Seedling dry weight indicated that XZN 1 was not affected by K-deficient